

SONNETS delivers an innovative methodological framework for public sector organisations and related stakeholders to accelerate the transformation of the public sector through the identification, analysis and take-up of emerging technologies that hold the potential to transform and infuse real value to public services.

OUR VISION

INFORMATION

Project Coordinator

Nuria Rodríguez
Atos Spain
nuria.rodriguez@atos.net

- @SonnetsProject
- Sonnets
- SONNETS project

www.sonnets-project.eu

Join our Expert
Advisory Group

Atos

Fraunhofer

SONNETS project is being financed by the European Commission under Grant agreement 692868.

SONNETS

SOCIETAL Needs aNalysis and
EMERGING Technologies in the public Sector

Transforming the public sector
into a technology and
innovation leader

LEGAL

- Eradication of corruption
- Transparency
- Accountability
- Legal and fiscal simplification

ORGANIZATIONAL

- Management by objectives vs. administrative fulfilment
- Meritocracy
- Value and customer orientation
- Effective communication of benefits
- Higher osmosis with private sector (start-ups / SMEs)

HUMAN CAPITAL

- Education and training
- Employees empowerment
- Leaving inflows of highly qualified youngsters

POLITICAL

- Long term global orientation
- Persistence and stratification of efforts
- Triple sustainability mind-set

SUCCESS FACTORS

For further information:

<http://www.sonnets-project.eu/content/results>

